

Mineral water bottling in Bulgaria

Vladimir Hristov, Simeon Valtchev, Mila Trayanova, Radostina Atanassova, Aleksey Benderev

Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 24, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria;
e-mails: vhh@geology.bas.bg; simeonwaltscheff@hotmail.co.uk; milatr@abv.bg; radi@geology.bas.bg;
alekseybenderev@yahoo.com

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Abstract. Bulgaria is rich in sources of mineral water of temperatures in the range of 25 °C–100 °C and various chemical compositions due to diverse geological and hydrogeological conditions. A large portion of the reservoirs of low-mineralisation water is suitable for bottling. Most of them are situated in Southern Bulgaria and related to fractured hydrothermal systems, while in Northern Bulgaria mineral waters of low mineralisation are formed in the relatively shallow levels of artesian aquifers. In the last 30 years, the utilisation of bottled mineral water has increased and, currently, there are at least 18 bottling facilities, while 12 others have closed down for various reasons. The purpose of the present study is to characterise the chemical composition of the Bulgarian mineral waters utilised for bottling, in terms of geological setting, quality, compliance with regulations and possible problems associated with mineral deposition and corrosion. The water type largely depends on the host rocks. In most cases, sodium-type waters are utilized and, in the case of anions, bicarbonate and sulphate. The only exceptions are the waters formed in limestone, dolomite and marble, which are calcium-bicarbonate and calcium-magnesium type.

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INTRODUCTION

Bottled water is becoming increasingly important for contemporary consumers and it is a part of daily life. In this respect, it is important that the quality of different bottled waters in the country is appropriate for consumer health. Generally, there are three main types of bottled waters: natural mineral, spring and potable. The spring water and natural mineral waters are bottled without treatment, while potable water is bottled after pre-treatment resulting in artificially altered chemical composition. The main requirement for spring water is to comply with drinking water regulations. Exceedance of upper level concentration of certain com-

ponents is sometimes allowed for therapeutic use under relevant restrictions. The suitability of mineral waters for bottling depends on their chemical composition and resource availability. The invariability of chemical composition and the absence of processes of precipitation of mineral phases over time are important.

Comparisons of bottled natural mineral waters from different countries and regions indicate considerable variance in chemical composition, depending on local geological conditions of formation, taste preferences of the local population and national regulations (Misund *et al.*, 1999; Wynn, 2009; Reimann and Birke, 2010; Birke *et al.*, 2010; Bertoldi *et al.*, 2011; Quattrini, 2016). Generalised

studies on the conditions of formation and quality comparisons of bottled natural mineral waters have been published in many countries. Examples include a number of studies from Austria (Kralik *et al.*, 2003), Croatia (Peh *et al.*, 2010), Estonia (Bityukova and Petersell, 2010), Germany (Birke *et al.*, 2010), Hungary (Fugedi, 2010), Italy (Cicchella *et al.*, 2010; Dinelli *et al.*, 2010, 2012; Quattrini *et al.*, 2016), Norway, Sweden, Finland and Iceland (Frengstad *et al.*, 2010), Poland (Gałarska *et al.*, 2016) Romania (Feru, 2004), Russia (Vorornov, 2000), Serbia (Petrović *et al.*, 2010, 2011), Slovenia (Brenčič *et al.*, 2010), Turkey (Pehlivan, 2007, Baba *et al.*, 2008), USA (Azoulay *et al.*, 2001).

The present paper considers only bottling of natural mineral waters in Bulgaria. The main objective is to analyse, systemise and compare bottled and marketed waters in Bulgaria, focusing on similarities and differences in quality depending on the geological conditions of formation and prospects for utilisation.

GEOLOGICAL AND HYDROGEOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

Populations on the territory of present-day Bulgaria have used thermal and mineral waters since ancient times. The conditions and factors for their formation, distribution, qualities and potential uses have been the subject of numerous studies (Dobrev, 1912; Penev, 1927; Azmanov, 1940; Kusitaseva and Melamed, 1958; Shterev, 1964; Petrov *et al.*, 1970; Velinov and Bojadgieva, 1981, 1998; Pentcheva *et al.*, 1997; Vladeva *et al.*, 2000; Bojadgieva and Gasharov, 2001; Bojadgieva *et al.*, 2010; Galabov and Stoyanov, 2011; Benderev *et al.*, 2016, Hristov *et al.*, 2019). Despite of the country's relatively small area of approximately 111,000 km², there are 630 springs and wells located in 170 geothermal fields. Approximately a third of the sources are being utilised (Petrov *et al.*, 1998). The geological and tectonic conditions determine the distribution, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of these waters. Rocks of different origin, lithological and petrographic composition are widespread on the territory of the country, with their age spanning from Precambrian to Quaternary.

There are different interpretations of the tectonic structure of the country (Yaranov, 1960; Bonchev, 1971; Yovchev, 1971; Zagorčev, 1992; Zagorchev, 1994; Dabovski *et al.*, 2002; Zagorchev, 2009); however, two main zones are distinguished: Northern and Southern Bulgaria. The Balkan Mountains,

predetermining the different conditions for the formation of both fresh (Antonov and Danchev, 1980) and thermal waters (Shterev, 1964; Petrov *et al.*, 1970; Benderev *et al.*, 2016) naturally divide these zones.

The entire area of Northern Bulgaria is located within the scope of a platform structure, the Moesian platform, which extends on the territory of Romania. A typical artesian basin was formed in this structure, composed of a number of stratified aquifers, with a general dip direction to the north. Lower-order tectonic structures make the spatial position of the aquifers more complex. Water temperature and total dissolved solids (TDS) increase significantly with depth, alongside with changes established in the chemical composition of natural minerals. TDS values vary from less than 1.0 g/L in the shallower levels of the aquifers to over 150 g/L in the deeper levels, where the waters are Cl-Na type. Thermal and mineral waters are formed in the deep aquifer levels composed of Paleogene clayey-sandy deposits and carbonate rocks of Triassic, Jurassic and Cretaceous ages. The so-called Upper Jurassic–Lower Cretaceous Aquifer is the most important in Northern Bulgaria.

Southern Bulgaria is characterised by complex fault structures as a result of tectonic plate displacements from the south, with the Rila-Rhodope Massif being a fragment of the overall structure (Yovchev, 1971). The mountains in this area are composed of Precambrian, Paleozoic and Mesozoic metamorphic, sedimentary, volcanic-sedimentary and intrusive rocks. A number of graben depressions formed within them, filled with Neozoic, mainly Plio-Quaternary sediments. The specific tectonic conditions are essential for the formation of different hydrogeological units and the interaction between them. The hydrothermal systems in this area are fracture type with thermo-mineral waters of temperatures up to approximately 100 °C and TDS rarely exceeding 1 g/L.

The Water Act (1999) specifies 102 of all hydrothermal fields in Bulgaria as exclusive state property. The rest 68 hydrothermal fields are municipal property and these have been granted to municipalities for a period of 20 years. The water is being used for different purposes, depending on chemical composition and temperature – balneology, spa, sport, recreation, green houses, heating, industrial uses (Hristov *et al.*, 2019). Part of the thermal water reservoirs comply with the requirements for chemical composition of drinking water (Vladeva and Kostadinov, 1996, 2007) and are suitable for bottling. Data on chemical composition of bottled water were published by Kaneva *et al.* (2012). Other publica-

tions include comparative analyses (Delcheva *et al.*, 2016; Lyubomirova *et al.*; 2020, Mihaylova *et al.*, 2021); however, not all bottled mineral waters were included.

LOCATION AND BOTTLING ACTIVITY

According to the Bulgarian Soft Drinks Association, in 2017 bottled natural mineral and spring waters contributed 50 million euros to the country's economy, which was more than 22% of the total production of soft drinks in that year. Bottling of natural mineral water was not common until

Fig. 1. Mihalkovo bottling factory for naturally carbonated water (picture source: <https://bestsearch.ai/result.php?q=михалково%20фабрика%20газирана%20вода>).

1990. The first bottling plant was built in the Mihalkovo geothermal field in 1956 (Fig. 1), which is known in the country for its naturally carbonated water, discovered by German researchers in the 1930s. In 1958, a French production line was installed in Gorna Banya, Sofia (Fig. 2), which at the time was the most advanced bottling facility in the

Fig. 2. Gorna Banya bottling factory (picture source: <https://www.gornabania1.bg/>).

Fig. 3. Production and suspended sites for bottling natural mineral waters in Bulgaria (May 2020; see Table 1): 1 – Zones of fracture type or fissure karst groundwater reservoirs; 2 – Quaternary–Neogene sediments in grabens; 3 – Operating bottling facilities; 4 – Suspended bottling facilities.

country. The mineral water is characterised by high pH > 9.5 and very low TDS, approximately 0.18 g/L. Bottling of mineral water from the Hisarya geothermal field commenced in the same year. The water there has been proven to have beneficial effect on kidney disorders. Up to 30 mineral water bottling plants have been built since the political change in Bulgaria in 1989. The development of bottling facilities has been irregular as different companies have been opening, closing down or operating intermittently for various reasons – unsuccessful marketing, technical challenges related to abstraction wells or distribution systems, insufficient quantities or unsatisfactory quality of the natural mineral water. Overall, there are 30 sites for bottling of natural mineral water in the National Register (Fig. 3).

Most of the bottling sites are located in the southwestern part of the country, where the mineral waters

are of appropriate quality. Registration of 12 bottling plants for natural mineral water was temporarily suspended in the period 2012–2017. Thus, in 2020, the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Environment and Water licensed only 18 companies (Fig. 3) and these are subject of the present study. Free CO₂ is added to some of the natural mineral waters (e.g., Sofia-Gorna Banya, Fig. 1) and these are being marketed as non-carbonated or carbonated varieties.

The sources for bottled mineral water are distributed in two great geotectonic areas (Fig. 3, Table 1). Only six sources are located in Northern Bulgaria, with one of them (Barziya) drawing its water from granites. The other sources are in limestone aquifers. The rest 24 natural mineral sources are located in Southern Bulgaria, where deep faults control the occurrence and flow of natural mineral water generated primarily in magmatic and metamorphic environments.

Table 1
Information on operating and suspended sources of bottled mineral water in Bulgaria

No	Site	Source	Lithology	Interval (depth, m)	T °C	pH	TDS mg/l	H ₂ SiO ₃ mg/l
Under exploitation								
1	Barziya	Well	Granite	108–425	32	9.4	257	84
2	Bankya	Well	Andesite	25–740	27	8.33	387	40
3	Gorna Banya 1	Well	Andesite	261–425	31.5	9.9	146	46
4	Gorna Banya 2	Spring	Andesite		19	9.18	136	40
5	Knyazhevo 1	Well	Andesite	75–481	35.5	9.51	129	46
6	Knyazhevo 2	Well	Andesite	264–320	20	9.97	134	28
7	Dolna Banya	Well	Sandstone	450–515	16.2	9.23	154	24
8	Velinograd	Well	Granite, gneiss	20–246	37.5	9.28	190	59
9	Banichan	Well	Dacite	316–600	18.3	8.49	295	32
10	Devin	Well	Sandstone	536–690	37	9.56	226	43
11	Mihalkovo	Well	Marble	52–76	24	6.58	2519	69
12	St. Zhelezare	Well	Granite	265–418	30	8.51	332	67
13	Hisar 1	Spring	Granite		26.8	8.51	234	55
14	Hisar 2	Well	Granite	150–660	49	8.99	231	58
15	Lenovo	Well	Rhyolite	108–180	20	8.39	318	32
16	Dragoynovo	Well	Sand	45–130	18.4	7.22	414	65
17	Shivachevo	Spring	Limestone		22.5	7.49	392	36
18	Voditsa	Well	Limestone	1275–90	41.2	7.81	443	24
Suspended exploitation								
19	Spanchevtsi	Well	Granite	100–633	31	8.68	197	45
20	Tr. Bankya	Spring	Limestone		20.2	7.36	422	12
21	Rudartsi	Well	Monzonite	51–301	26	9.03	271	36
22	Nevestino	Well	Diorite	139–267	31	9.58	766	51
23	Katuntsi	Well	Sandstone	15–291	27.9	9.38	338	26
24	Rakitovo	Well	Gneiss	36–216	19	9.35	299	33
25	Belovo	Well	Marble	83–96	23.3	7.58	554	17
26	Bratsigovo	Well	Rhyolite	62–404	20.3	7.04	395	77
27	Voyvodinovo	Well	Sand	360–428	31	7.9	604	28
28	Shrpkovo	Well	Dolomite	145–433	31.7	7.52	811	18
29	Boaza	Well	Limestone	432–454	25.3	8.02	614	21
30	Kavarna	Well	Limestone	660–1097	25.1	7.87	520	25

In the northern region, the mineral waters discharge from granitic outcrops (Barziya) or Mesozoic sediment rocks (limestone and dolomite). In this region, geothermal waters normally have high TDS (>1–150 g/L). Only a very few of them, with TDS <1 g/L, are bottled.

In the southern region, the situation is rather different. More than 95% of natural mineral springs and sources have TDS <1 g/L. That is why most of the mineral sources and the bottling companies in the country are located in this region. The only source of naturally carbonated water in Bulgaria, which is bottled in Mihalkovo, located in the southern part of the country among metamorphic rocks and has TDS higher than 2.5 g/L.

QUALITIES OF BOTTLED NATURAL MINERAL WATERS

Output information

In the last three decades, all 30 sources of bottled mineral water in Bulgaria have been tested as part of the licensing procedure. The analytical results form the basis of the quality characterisation in the Register of Balneotherapy Assessments issued by the Ministry of Health (<https://www.mh.government.bg/bg/administrativni-uslugi/registri/registr-na-izdadenite-ot-mz-balneologichni-ocenki-za-mineralni-v>).

The results for 46 components are taken under consideration: major components (SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , F⁻, HCO_3^- , Cl⁻, HSiO_3^- , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , NH_4^+ , Na, K, Ca, Mg, H_2SiO_3), several minor components (Li, Fe, Mn, Al, As, Sn, Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Se, Hg, Zn, Ba, B, Ag), gases (He, CO_2 and H_2S), radionuclides (U, Ra, Rn, ^3H , α - and β -activity, indicative dose), general parameters measured *in-situ* and in laboratory (pH, TDS, electrical conductivity) and some microbiological components. Assessments for balneotherapy, drinking water quality and possible use for medical purposes are also presented. The data are supplemented with previously published results (Azmanov, 1940; Kusitaseva and Melamed, 1958; Petrov *et al.*, 1970; Vladeva *et al.*, 2000). Pentcheva *et al.* (1997) published the most essential data. The study was undertaken at higher analytical accuracy and improved sensitivity, including a number of rare and trace components, as well as the presence of inert gases – helium, argon, etc. Information about lithology, abstraction type and depth and selected parameters are presented in Table 1.

The data show that the bottled waters in Bulgaria contain <1 g/L TDS, with the only exception being the naturally carbonated water from Mihalkovo with >2.5 g/L TDS. With regard to therapeutic

effects, the bottled waters are characterised by relatively high pH values and H_2SiO_3 content. The type of water largely depends on the host rocks. In most cases, the utilized water is sodium-type, and in terms of anions – bicarbonate and sulphate types. The only exceptions are the waters formed within limestone, dolomite and marble, which are calcium-bicarbonate and calcium-magnesium types (Fig. 4).

In terms of minor components, the bottled water is of different composition, depending on local geological and hydrogeological conditions. Data from the certification testing indicate that iron concentrations are <0.2 mg/L, with one exception at Dragoyново (0.56 mg/L), and aluminium concentrations are <0.1 mg/L, with one exception at Mihalkovo (0.16 mg/L). Other components are present in relatively broader ranges: zinc, from 0.01 mg/L to 0.112 mg/L (Belovo); boron, from 0.05 mg/L to 0.966 mg/L (Boaza); barium, from 0.01 mg/L to 0.103 mg/L (Shivachevo). Lithium was detected in concentrations slightly above detection limits in the water of six out of 30 sources, manganese in four sources, and arsenic in three sources. The data by Pencheva *et al.* (1997) and our unpublished data show that these components are found in trace concentrations in almost all tested sources of bottled water. In addition, some components not listed in the license certificates are detected in low concentrations: Ag, Au, Ba, Be, Bi, Ce, Cs, Ga, Ge, Hg, La, Mo, Nd, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sm, Sn, Sr, Ti, V, W. The radioactivity parameters with value ranges are given in Table 2.

Nitrogen acratotherms are the predominant water types, except for the water from Mihalkovo with CO_2 concentration of 1,154 mg/L. Carbon dioxide in lower concentrations between 0.013 mg/L and 21 mg/L is detected in half of the water sources. Most of the certified waters contain H_2S with concentrations up to 2.81 mg/L (Voditsa).

The certificates indicate that most waters used for drinking balneotherapy and balneoprophylaxis have a beneficial effect on some gastrointestinal (*e.g.*, chronic gastritis, gastroduedenitis, peptic ulcer disease, enterocolitis), biliary-hepatic (gallstones, chronic hepatitis, biliary dyskinesia, etc.), renal and urological (chronic pyelonephritis, chronic cystitis, biliary dyskinesia, urate and oxalate lithiasis, etc.) and metabolic (gout, diabetes, obesity) disorders.

Assessment of qualities according to regulations

All available chemical data for the thirty mineral water sources were screened against the Bulgarian

Fig. 4. Piper diagram.

Table 2
Radionuclide characteristics of Bulgarian bottled water

Radionuclide components	Minimum value	Maximum value	Sites with maximum value
Alpha radioactivity, Bq/l	0.1	0.293	Staro Zhelezare
Beta radioactivity, Bq/l	0.058	0.327	Shipkovo
Ra, Bq/l	0.002	1.95	Shipkovo
Rn, Bq/l	4.3	103.4	Hisar
U, mg/l	0.00002	0.023	Bratsigovo

regulatory requirements (Regulation Nr 9/2001 for the qualities of the waters used for drinking and domestic purposes). The concentrations are below the upper limits for Cl^- , CO_3^{2-} , HCO_3^- , H_2SiO_3 , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , Li, Na, K, Mg, Mn, Al, Sn, Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Se, Hg, Zn, Ba, gases CO_2 and H_2S as well as for U, Ra, Rn, ^3H and β -activity. Exceedances of the regulatory limits for some of the other components are exceptions and are discussed below.

The TDS data are shown in Table 1. Most Bulgarian bottled waters have TDS up to 500 mg/L, which characterises them as very fresh water with low mineralisation.

The Bulgarian regulatory upper TDS limit is 1,000 mg/L. All bottled water in the country meets this regulatory requirement, with the exception of the water from Mihalkovo (TDS 2,519 mg/L). As a result of the elevated TDS, the water from this source

has elevated concentrations of fluoride (2.89 mg/l), SO_4^{2-} (263.77 mg/L), Ca (190.38 mg/L), electrical conductivity (2710 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), As (0.066 mg/L) and B (1.539 mg/L). Despite exceeding the maximum concentrations for these components, the naturally carbonated water from Mihalkovo has long been established in the domestic and the international market.

The main problem for the bottling of natural mineral waters in Southern Bulgaria is the increased concentration of fluorides, which will be separately considered. High fluoride mineral water consumption may have some toxic effects if fluoride intake is above 10 mg/L, *e.g.*, dental fluorosis, skeletal fluorosis. For this reason, the Bulgarian drinking water standard is 1.5 mg/L for fluoride in potable water and 5 mg/L for bottled natural mineral water. Figure 5 shows the fluoride concentrations of all bottled natural mineral waters.

The maximum fluoride concentration of 5 mg/L is exceeded in two sources of natural mineral water: Nevestino and Rakitovo (Nos 22 and 24 in Table 1). For this reason, both sources were decommissioned. There are eight sources of bottled mineral water with fluoride concentration between 1.5 mg/L and 5.0 mg/L (Fig. 5) and these are not recommended

for consumption by children younger than 7 years old. Figure 6 summarizes the analytical results for pH of the natural mineral water samples. The pH of the water from all considered sources is above the minimum value of pH = 6.5 set in Regulation No 9/2001. The upper limit of pH = 9 is slightly exceeded in two sources of natural mineral water, Gorna Banya-1 and Knyazhevo-2 (Nos 3 and 6 in Table 1). However, both are widely recognised as waters with most suitable qualities for bottling in Bulgaria.

The values of the other hydrochemical parameters were screened against the Bulgarian drinking water standards in Table 3. The results show that most of the mineral water sources currently used for bottling meet the regulatory requirements. The main exception is the naturally carbonated water from Mihalkovo, which, in addition to the elevated TDS (Table 1) and the associated relatively high electrical conductivity, has concentrations exceeding the standards for sulphates, sodium, barium and iron. The maximum iron concentration is exceeded in the water source Dragoyново. Elevated radionuclide parameters (α - and β -radioactivity) have been found in six of the water sources currently used for

Fig. 5. Fluoride concentration in sources of bottled natural mineral water.

Table 3
Hydrochemical parameters of water sources used for bottling

		SO ₄ ²⁻ mg/l	NH ₄ ⁺ mg/l	Na ⁺ mg/l	Ca ²⁺ mg/l	Fe mg/l	EC µs/cm	As mg/l	B mg/l	α-rad. Bq/l	β-rad. Bq/l
	Maximum concentration	250	0.5	200	150	0.2	2000	0.01	1	0.1	1
Under exploitation											
1	Barziya	33.95	<0.05	46.33	2	0.03	270	<0.01	0.161	0.118	0.108
2	Bankya	109.05	<0.05	90.26	11.58	0.01	457	<0.01	0.161	<0.02	0.228
3	Gorna Banya 1	19.96	<0.05	31.63	1.7	0.03	169.3	<0.01	<0.05	0.021	0.058
4	Gorna Banya 2	12.55	<0.05	31.94	1.9	0.01	169	<0.01	0.023	<0.027	0.083
5	Knyazhevo 1	13.79	<0.05	28.54	1.8	0.01	138.9	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	0.071
6	Knyazhevo 2	16.67	<0.05	33.35	1.2	0.08	179	<0.01	0.099	<0.027	0.085
7	Dolna Banya	29.63	<0.05	38.73	2.2	0.03	197.6	<0.01	0.158	0.032	0.07
8	Velinograd	24.48	<0.05	37.4	2	0.02	210	<0.01	0.064	0.044	0.113
9	Banichan	24.69	<0.05	66	8.42	0.03	316	<0.01	0.247	0.77	0.264
10	Devin	19.75	<0.05	55.91	1.3	0.03	265	<0.01	0.103	0.038	0.037
11	Mihalkovo	263.77	<0.05	413.8	190.38	0.09	2710	0.066	1.539	0.55	1.9
12	Staro Zhelezare	30.45	<0.05	61.2	8.02	0.02	327	<0.01	0.191	0.293	0.22
13	Hisar 1	23.66	<0.05	49.95	5.01	0.03	254	<0.01	0.173	0.01	0.106
14	Hisar 2	28.6	<0.05	50.3	3.11	0.03	250	<0.01	0.098	0.156	0.217
15	Lenovo	47.53	<0.05	72.75	7.01	0.04	374	<0.01	0.096	<0.038	0.085
16	Dragoynovo	13.92	<0.05	35.24	37.05	0.56	411	0.017	0.194	0.154	0.434
17	Shivachevo	16.05	<0.05	5.3	50.1	0.02	422	0.22	0.131	0.116	0.141
18	Voditsa	57.2	<0.05	29.01	47.49	0.02	462	<0.01	0.067	0.152	0.224
Suspended exploitation											
19	Spanchevtsi	24.07	<0.05	32.17	7.52	0.01	182.5	<0.01	0.203	0.154	0.096
20	Transka Bankya	4.53	<0.05	3.78	71.36	0.03	476	<0.01	0.203	0.147	0.128
21	Rudartsi	90.94	<0.05	63.09	6.07	0.03	359	<0.01	0.219	0.05	0.054
22	Nevestino	295.78	0.53	229.26	1.8	0.02	1079	<0.01	2.48	0.183	0.164
23	Katuntsi	15.23	<0.05	92.68	1.8	0.03	410	<0.01	0.17	0.066	0.179
24	Rakitovo	112.55	<0.05	78.21	2.3	0.04	458	<0.01	0.574	0.11	0.101
25	Belovo	30.25	<0.05	16.07	76.15	0.03	575	<0.01	0.111	0.137	0.24
26	Bratsigovo	9.47	<0.05	44.95	29.36	0.24	364	<0.01	0.114	0.74	0.242
27	Voyvodinovo	125.5	0	115.5	17.3		604				0.02
28	Shrpkovo	367.88	<0.05	8.26	171.34	0.15	916	<0.01	0.17	0.613	0.327
29	Boaza	63.65	0.55	132.1	10.69	0.2	685	<0.01	0.966	0.096	0.194
30	Kavarna	19.57	0.16	49.26	39.28	0.06	775	<0.01	0.199	0.19	0.208

bottling. According to Regulation No 9 on the quality of water intended for drinking and household purposes, these two parameters are only indicative and not restrictive. In the cases where these indicative values are exceeded, it is obligatory to determine individual indicative doses. This has been undertaken for the corresponding water sources and the obtained values are lower than upper level of 0.1 µSv/year.

Table 3 shows that the regulatory standards are not met for three parameters in the water from Nevestino, two parameters in the water from Shipkovo, Bratsigovo and Boaza. In addition, for most of them, α-radioactivity is also elevated. This fact and the elevated fluoride concentrations in Nevestino

and Rakitovo explain why operation was suspended at these bottling facilities.

Corrosion and scaling

The technological problems associated with bottling of mineral water include possible scaling and corrosion that can affect the facilities, as well as formation of sludge during retention of bottled water. In the present study, a preliminary assessment has been undertaken with regards to the likelihood of these processes occurring. Express empirical coefficients were introduced by Langelier (1936) – Langelier Saturation Index (LSI), and by Ryznar (1944) – Ryznar Stability Index (RSI). Based

on these indices, relevant classifications were developed (Carrier, 1965). LSI is a qualitative index and shows the trend of processes related to scaling or corrosion, while RSI evaluates it quantitatively, showing the degree of water saturation with CaCO_3 . The evaluation requires data on pH, temperature, TDS, hardness and alkalinity of thermal waters. The results of the evaluation are presented in Figs 6, 7. Most of the water sources are mainly

corrosive and have a relatively low probability of scaling. The latter is also confirmed by the assessment of saturation indices with respect to calcite (SI) (Garrels and Christ, 1965; Thraillkill, 1976). The values for all water sources are negative (Fig. 8), indicating that there is no likelihood of scaling of this mineral phase, which most often creates problems with the formation of sediments in mineral waters.

Fig. 6. pH data of bottled natural mineral water sources (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 7. LSI (a) and RSI (b) values and the Carrier (1965) classes of water used for bottling.

Fig. 8. Values of saturation index with respect to calcite of bottled water.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the present study of bottled natural mineral waters in Bulgaria, the following conclusions can be made:

- Analyses of 46 components in natural mineral waters bottled from 30 sources in Bulgaria show a wide spread in composition for most of the components. The quality of most of the bottled waters corresponds to the Bulgarian drinking water standards (Regulation No 9/2001 for the qualities of the waters used for drinking and domestic purposes). Bottling of 12 commercial brands of mineral water has been suspended as a result of noncompliance with the regulatory requirements, or for other reasons;
- The chemical composition of the natural mineral water depends on the geological environment of their formation. Most of the bottling facilities are in Southern Bulgaria and utilise fresh water from fractured aquifers in igneous or metamorphic siliceous rocks. There are several facilities in Northern Bulgaria, most

of which bottling water from the Upper Jurassic–Lower Cretaceous aquifer;

- Fluoride concentration exceeds the drinking water standard of 1.5 mg/L in 10 of the studied sources. Such water is not recommended for consumption by children under the age of 7 years and such water shall be labelled accordingly;
- Most of the water sources are generally corrosive and have a relatively low probability of scaling.

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